

The neuroanatomical substrates of autism and ADHD and their link to putative genomic underpinnings

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41 **Keywords:** ASD; ADHD; neurodevelopmental disorders; comorbidity; imaging-genetics;
42 structural MRI

43

44 **Abstract**

45 **Background:** Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are neurodevelopmental conditions
46 accompanied by differences in brain development. Neuroanatomical differences in autism are
47 variable across individuals and likely underpin distinct clinical phenotypes. To parse
48 heterogeneity, it is essential to establish how the neurobiology of ASD is modulated by
49 differences associated with co-occurring conditions, such as attention-deficit/hyperactivity
50 disorder (ADHD). This study aimed to (i) investigate between-group differences in autistic
51 individuals with and without co-occurring ADHD, and to (ii) link these variances to putative
52 genomic underpinnings.

53 **Methods:** We examined differences in cortical thickness (CT) and surface area (SA) and their
54 genomic associations in a sample of 533 individuals from the Longitudinal European Autism
55 Project. Using a general linear model including main effects of autism and ADHD, and an
56 ASD-by-ADHD interaction, we examined to which degree ADHD modulates the autism-
57 related neuroanatomy. Further, leveraging the spatial gene expression data of the Allen Human
58 Brain Atlas, we identified genes whose spatial expression patterns resemble our neuroimaging
59 findings.

60 **Results:** In addition to significant main effects for ASD and ADHD in fronto-temporal, limbic,
61 and occipital regions, we observed a significant ASD-by-ADHD interaction in the left
62 precentral gyrus and the right frontal gyrus for measures of CT and SA, respectively. Moreover,
63 individuals with ASD+ADHD differed in CT to those without. Both main effects and the
64 interaction were enriched for ASD - but not for ADHD-related genes.

65 **Limitations:** Although we employed a multicenter design to overcome single-site recruitment
66 limitations, our sample size of $N = 25$ individuals in the ADHD only group is relatively small
67 compared to the other subgroups, which limits the generalizability of the results. Also, we
68 assigned subjects into ADHD positive groupings according to the DSM-5 rating scale. While

69 this is sufficient for obtaining a research diagnosis of ADHD, our approach did not take into
70 account for how long the symptoms have been present, which is typically considered when
71 assessing ADHD in the clinical setting.

72 **Conclusion:** Thus, our findings suggest that the neuroanatomy of ASD is significantly
73 modulated by ADHD, and that autistic individuals with co-occurring ADHD may have specific
74 neuroanatomical underpinnings potentially mediated by atypical gene expression.

75 **Introduction**

76 Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are highly heterogeneous neurodevelopmental conditions
77 characterized by differences in social interaction and communication, alongside restricted,
78 repetitive behaviors and interests (1). These features are associated with a different
79 development of the brain (2), and regional differences in neuroanatomy (3,4). Yet,
80 neuroanatomical differences in autism are highly variable across individuals, and likely
81 underpin different clinical phenotypes.

82 Autism is a condition with a high prevalence of co-occurring conditions. More specifically,
83 72% autistic adolescents have at least one co-occurring psychiatric disorder, and often meet
84 diagnostic criteria for two or more co-occurring conditions (5). Among these, attention-
85 deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is the most prevalent, with estimates ranging between
86 16-80% of autistic individuals also having a clinical diagnosis of ADHD (5–8). The large range
87 in prevalence estimates has mainly been attributed to variability in diagnostic methods
88 employed (5,6,8). Given the large degree of co-occurrence between autism and ADHD, it is
89 likely that inter-individual differences in the neuroanatomy of autism are confounded by the
90 severity and nature of ADHD features, and so contribute to the highly complex clinical and
91 neurobiological phenotype that is characteristic for autism. Overall, autism is characterized by
92 neuroanatomical differences in several large-scale neural systems that include fronto-temporal
93 and fronto-parietal regions, the amygdala-hippocampal complex, the cerebellum, basal ganglia,

94 and anterior and posterior cingulate regions (2–4). Many of these brain regions overlap with
95 core components of the so called ‘social’ brain network, which comprises a set of brain regions
96 that mediate functions related to social cognition and/or emotional processing (9). Similarly,
97 ADHD has been linked to neuroanatomical differences in frontal regions (e.g. dorsolateral and
98 ventromedial prefrontal cortex), the parietal cortex, cingulate cortices, basal ganglia, the limbic
99 lobe (e.g. amygdala and hippocampus) and the cerebellum (10–12). There is thus a large degree
100 of overlap between the neural networks underpinning autism and ADHD. Even though the
101 neural systems subserving autism and ADHD seem to overlap to a large degree,
102 neuroanatomical differences between both conditions have also been reported. For example,
103 the neuroanatomical differences in the temporal lobe are less commonly reported in ADHD
104 than in autism, while differences in cingulate brain regions seem to be more common in ADHD
105 than autism. Moreover, it has been reported that individuals with ADHD (without co-occurring
106 autism) have significantly reduced grey matter (GM) volume in fronto-temporal areas relative
107 to autistic individuals, as well as significantly increased volume in parietal areas (13). Another
108 study reported that, compared controls, autistic individuals show increased cortical thickness
109 (CT), while individuals with ADHD show for example decreased CT across the brain (14).
110 Taken together, these studies suggest that ASD and ADHD may have separable
111 neuroanatomical underpinnings.

112 So far, only few studies have explored the neuroanatomy of autism with co-occurring ADHD.
113 A study by Mizuno et al. (15) reported that autistic individuals with co-occurring ADHD have
114 significantly decreased volume in the left postcentral gyrus compared to typically developing
115 controls (15). However, as this study only examined individuals with a diagnosis of both autism
116 and ADHD relative to neurotypical controls, it was not possible to disentangle the relative
117 impact of autism and ADHD on the level of brain anatomy. Another study observed significant
118 differences in grey matter volume and surface area (SA) in the post- and precentral gyrus when

119 comparing individuals with autism to individuals with autism and ADHD (16). Further, there
120 are reports of significant ASD-by-ADHD interactions in the parietal, temporal and limbic lobe
121 for measures of CT, and in the right cingulate cortex for measures of cortical volume (17).
122 However, in this study, the interaction terms did not survive multiple comparison correction
123 (17). Neuroanatomical variability may therefore exist not only between neurodevelopmental
124 conditions, but also between distinct measures of neuroanatomy.

125 Traditional investigations of brain structure have mainly focused on cortical volume, measured
126 on the whole-brain, regional, and/or vertex-level. However, cortical volume is, by definition,
127 the product of two different cortical features, namely CT and SA. Previous research by our
128 group has shown that measures of brain volume, therefore, do not characterize a specific (i.e.,
129 unique) aspect of the neural architecture, but can be explained by separable variations in CT
130 and SA (e.g., (18)). These two morphometric features also have distinct genetic determinants
131 and developmental trajectories (19–22). Thus, to characterize neuroanatomical variability
132 associated with ASD and/or ADHD, it is important to investigate CT and SA separately. Using
133 data provided by the EU-AIMS Longitudinal European Autism Project (LEAP; (23)), a large-
134 scale European research collaboration on autism, we therefore examined the neuroanatomical
135 underpinnings of autism with and without co-occurring ADHD symptomatology based on
136 measures of CT and SA. Given the conceptual complexity of both ASD and ADHD (24–26),
137 we utilized a categorical rather than a dimensional design that allowed us to establish the extent
138 to which ADHD symptoms modulate the neuroanatomy of autism.

139 Moreover, leveraging the spatial gene expression data provided by the Allen Human Brain
140 Atlas (AHBA; (27)) we aimed at linking these neuroanatomical differences to putative
141 molecular underpinnings. Overall, neuropsychiatric conditions are highly heritable with an
142 estimated heritability of 83% for autism (28), and 75% for ADHD (29). However, the genetic
143 architecture of autism is complex, involving hundreds (or more) genetic variants that mediate

144 wider autism traits (30). Many of these genes map onto biological pathways underpinning
145 neural development (30–32). The genetic architecture of ADHD is equally complex, and
146 implicates mechanisms underpinning early embryonic development and cognitive abilities
147 (33). Previous studies also suggest that there is a significant genetic overlap between autism
148 and ADHD. Overall, the genetic correlation between both conditions is 0.37 (34), which is
149 higher than the genetic correlation between autism and other psychiatric disorders (e.g., $r =$
150 0.22 for autism and schizophrenia (SCZ), $r = 0.14$ for autism and bipolar disorder; (34)).
151 Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) report several single nucleotide polymorphisms
152 (SNPs) that are significantly associated with autism or ADHD, and a significant overlap
153 between the SNPs associated with autism and those associated with ADHD has been reported
154 (35). These SNPs map onto genes that are predominantly expressed in the brain, and play a
155 crucial role in neuronal migration, neuronal development, neuromodulation of
156 neurotransmission, and in general brain development (35). In the present study, we therefore
157 also examined whether brain regions where the neuroanatomy of autism is significantly
158 modulated by ADHD are enriched for genes that have previously been linked to autism and/or
159 ADHD on the genetic and transcriptomic level.

160

161 **Methods and Materials:**

162 **Participants**

163 This study utilized data provided by the EU-AIMS LEAP project (23), which is a European
164 multicenter study on stratification biomarkers for autism (www.aims-2-trials.eu). A
165 comprehensive description of the sample has been published elsewhere (23). In brief, the total
166 sample for which usable structural MRI data were available included $N = 638$ individuals (N
167 $= 359$ with ASD and $N = 279$ non-autistic controls). For the present study, a subset of $N = 533$

168 individuals aged between 6-30 years was selected that included all individuals with available
169 data from the ADHD DSM-5 rating scale (1) (Table 1). Based on autism diagnostic criteria
170 according to DSM-IV (36), DSM-IV-TR (37), DSM-5 (1), or ICD-10 (38) and whether
171 participants met criteria for ADHD according to the ADHD DSM-5 rating scale (1), we
172 subdivided the autistic individuals into two subgroups: ASD only (N = 170; 112 males, 58
173 females) and ASD with co-occurring ADHD (further referred to as ASD+ADHD group (N =
174 142; 107 males, 35 females)). From the neurodiverse control group without an ASD diagnosis,
175 we collected those individuals who met criteria for ADHD as a third subgroup (further referred
176 to as ADHD only group (N = 25; 14 males, 11 females)) and those who did not meet ADHD
177 criteria as our fourth subgroup (further referred to as typically developing (TD) controls (N =
178 196; 124 males, 72 females)). The ADHD DSM-5 rating scale was based on either parent- or
179 self-report scores depending on participants' age. For this study we used the categorical output
180 of the ADHD rating scale, which measures the presence of symptoms, evaluated on a 0-3 scale
181 (0 = not at all to 3 = very often). To be evaluated with a clinical concern, a participant must at
182 least score six responses with a 2 or 3 ("Often", "Very Often") (for more details see (23)).
183 Therefore, the rating scale output is not a clinical diagnosis per se but the symptom count is a
184 proxy for one. Notably, subsets were not matched for age, IQ, and sex to maximize the available
185 sample size. We therefore controlled for these measures in all subsequent analyses (see below).
186 Given the wide range in full scale IQ (FSIQ) across individuals, we also repeated our analyses
187 in a smaller subset of individuals, which excluded participants with a mild intellectual disability
188 (ID, i.e., FSIQ < 70). The results of these analyses are presented in the Additional file: Effects
189 of Intellectual Disability. For further details on demographics and exclusion criteria see
190 Additional file: Sample Description. An independent ethics committee at each site approved
191 the study, and written informed consent was obtained for all participants.

192 **MRI data acquisition**

193 All participants underwent MR imaging in 3-T scanners, at six different sites (University of
194 Cambridge and King’s College London, U.K.; Central Institute for Mental Health, Mannheim,
195 Germany; Radboud University Medical Centre and University Medical Centre Utrecht, the
196 Netherlands; Rome University, Italy). High-resolution structural T1-weighted volumetric
197 images were acquired with full head coverage, at 1.2-mm thickness with 1.2 x 1.2-mm in-plane
198 resolution (see Additional file: Table S1 for details).

199 **Cortical Surface Reconstructions Using FreeSurfer**

200 Usable structural MRI data were initially available for 708 individuals in the LEAP sample.
201 FreeSurfer v6.0.0 software (<http://surfer.nmr.mgh.harvard.edu/>) was used to derive models of
202 the cortical surface for each T₁-weighted image. These well-validated and fully automated
203 procedures have been previously described elsewhere (39–43). Each reconstructed surface
204 underwent strict quality assessments (see Additional file: MRI Data Quality Assessments),
205 resulting in a final sample of $N = 638$ individuals (44). In brief, three independent raters judged
206 the quality of each scan with three possible decisions: include, exclude, edit (44). In our study,
207 we examined measures of CT and SA. Measures of CT were computed as the closest distance
208 from the outer (i.e., pial) to the inner (i.e., white matter) boundary at each vertex on the
209 tessellated surface (43). Measures of surface area were quantified as the area of the cortex at a
210 given point on the cortical surface (i.e., the sum of faces in the polygon mesh representation of
211 the cortex at a particular vertex) as previously described by Winkler et al. (45). For each
212 participant we also computed mean CT across the entire brain (CT_0), as well as total SA
213 (SA_{total}). To improve detection of population changes, each parameter was smoothed using a
214 15-mm surface based smoothing kernel.

215 **Surface-Based Statistical Analyses of Cortical Thickness and Surface Area**

216 Statistical analyses were performed using the SurfStat toolbox
217 (<https://www.math.mcgill.ca/keith/surfstat/>) for MATLAB version R2021a

218 (<https://www.mathworks.com>), and R for Statistical Computing (www.r-project.org). Vertex-
219 wise differences in neuroanatomy (Y) were quantified using a general linear model (GLM)
220 with (1) ASD, ADHD, sex, and site (see Additional file: Site effects for further details, also
221 using ComBat batch correction) as fixed-effect factors, (2) an ASD-by-ADHD interaction term,
222 and (3) linear and quadratic age, FSIQ, and a total brain-measure (i.e. CT_0 or SA_{total}
223 respectively) as continuous covariates:

$$224 Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ASD + \beta_2 ADHD + \beta_3 ASD * ADHD + \beta_4 Sex + \beta_5 Age + \beta_6 Age^2 + \beta_7 FSIQ + \\ 225 \beta_8 Site + \beta_9 totalBrain + \varepsilon_i$$

226 where ε_i is the residual error at vertex i . Continuous covariates were mean centered across
227 groups to improve interpretability of the coefficients. Corrections for multiple comparisons
228 across the whole brain were performed using random field theory (RFT) based cluster analysis
229 with a cluster-forming and cluster-based threshold of $p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). Effect sizes associated
230 with each model term were assessed using *Cohen's f*, where values of 0.25, 0.5, and 0.75
231 indicate small, medium, and large effects, respectively.

232 To specifically identify neuroanatomical differences between ASD individuals with and
233 without a co-occurring diagnosis of ADHD, we fitted an additional GLM on a subset of the
234 total sample that only included participants with ASD, and examined the main effect of ADHD
235 ($N = 312$), i.e.,

$$236 Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Group + \beta_2 Sex + \beta_3 Age + \beta_4 Age^2 + \beta_5 FSIQ + \beta_6 Site + \beta_7 totalBrain + \varepsilon_i$$

237 **Gene Expression Decoding Analysis**

238 To link our neuroanatomical findings to putative genomic underpinnings, we leveraged the
239 spatial gene expression data from the Allen Human Brain Atlas (AHBA; (27)) to identify a list
240 of genes with a spatial pattern of expression that resembles the neuroanatomical patterns
241 highlighted by our statistical neuroimaging analyses. To this aim, we initially uploaded the

242 statistical t-maps associated with the main effect of ASD, the main effect of ADHD, as well as
243 the ASD-by-ADHD interaction term for CT and SA (Figure 4A & 4C) to the Neurovault server
244 (<https://neurovault.org>). Next, using python code embedded within Neurovault and Neurosynth
245 (<https://neurosynth.org>), we performed a gene expression decoding analysis that statistically
246 assesses the spatial correlation between our statistical maps and the pattern of gene expression
247 for each of a total of 20,787 protein coding genes (46). To do so, the six AHBA donor brains
248 are initially co-registered with the MNI atlas (also used by FreeSurfer) using nonlinear
249 registration (transcriptomic alignment). At each sampling site (i.e. probe), a spherical region-
250 of-interest (ROI) is drawn (default radius $r = 4\text{mm}$), and the statistical test parameter in each
251 FreeSurfer overlay was averaged within each ROI. This resulted in a spatial vector of values
252 for each donor, which was subsequently correlated with the normalized gene expression data.
253 Here, the analysis constructs a linear model for each donor brain, where the slopes encode the
254 spatial correlation between each gene's expression pattern to the statistical neuroimaging map
255 (random effects model). In line with the input maps, these analyses were restricted to cortical
256 tissue. The slopes are then subjected to a one-sample t-test to identify genes whose spatial
257 expression patterns are consistently highly similar to the imaging maps (i.e. across donor
258 brains). The derived list of genes was thresholded at $p < 0.01$. We chose this 'liberal' threshold
259 as this analysis did not constitute a hypothesis test *per se*, but rather a selection step aimed at
260 yielding an initial list of genes for the subsequent enrichment analyses. Given that both sides
261 of our imaging contrasts were of equal relevance, we considered both positive and negative t-
262 statistic values.

263 In addition to the Neurosynth decoding approach, we performed gene expression decoding
264 using a General Least Squares (GLS) approach that also accounted for spatial autocorrelations
265 in embedded transcriptomic maps, to assess the robustness of our findings. The GLS approach
266 is described in detail in Additional file: General Least Square (GLS)-decoding.

267

268 **Gene Enrichment Analyses**

269 Next, we performed several gene enrichment analyses to establish the biological relevance and
270 functional role of decoded genes. All enrichment testing was performed using the GeneOverlap
271 package in R (10.18129/B9.bioc.GeneOverlap). Specifically, we tested the decoded gene-lists
272 for an enrichment with different gene-sets known to be associated with ASD at the genetic and
273 transcriptomic level. At the genetic level, this included the 102 rare and de novo protein
274 truncating variants identified in the largest exome sequencing study of autism world-wide (47).
275 We also included an ASD-related gene list compiled by SFARI (categories S, 1, 2, & 3
276 downloaded in November 2020 from <https://gene.sfari.org/>). At the transcriptomic level, we
277 included a list of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) (upregulated/downregulated) in post-
278 mortem cortex tissue in ASD (48), and genes that are differentially expressed in specific cell
279 types in ASD (49). Moreover, we included genes from differentially expressed co-expression
280 modules in ASD that map onto specific biological processes (50). ADHD-related genes were
281 derived based on a GWAS study published by Demontis and colleagues (33). Here, we used
282 the MAGMA plug-in on the FUMA GWAS annotation platform (<https://fuma.ctglab.nl>) to
283 perform a GWAS analysis (51). Here, variants were mapped onto genes based on their exact
284 position, and aggregated association p-values were calculated for each gene. Taking into
285 account the sample composition, a European ancestry reference from 1000 Genomes phase 3
286 was used as reference panel. Bonferroni correction was used to set the significance threshold
287 (correcting for all $N = 10,894$ gene sets tested from MsigdB v5.2; (52)) The resulting gene list
288 consisted of $N = 22$ ADHD-related genes, which was used for further gene enrichment
289 analyses. Our enrichment tests generated enrichment odds ratios, hypergeometric p-values, and
290 FDR-corrected p-values using a background total of the 20,787 Neurosynth genes. Last, we
291 examined the percentage overlap between genes associated with both main effects and the

292 interaction term relative to the total number of genes significantly associated with the imaging
 293 phenotypes (see Additional file: Figure S7 for details).

294

295 Results

296 Subject Demographics

297 There was no significant difference in the ratio of males to females between any of the four
 298 subgroups ($p = 0.06642$) (Table 1). There was, however, a significant difference in age between
 299 the ASD group and the co-occurring group (ASD only: 18.45 ± 5.6 ; ASD+ADHD: 16.38 ± 5.30 ;
 300 $p = 0.0061$) (Table 1). Subgroups also differed significantly in FSIQ ($p < 2e-16$) (with TD
 301 having the highest IQ (108.44 ± 14.1) and the ADHD only group the lowest (79.8 ± 21.1)) (Table
 302 1). We therefore covaried for these potential confounds in all subsequent analyses.

303 **Table 1: Characteristics of participants with ASD, ADHD, ASD+ADHD and control**
 304 **subjects.^a**

Variable	ASD only (n=170)		ADHD only (n=25)		ASD+ADHD (n=142)		TD (n=196)		Analysis		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	X ²	df	p
Sex									7.18	3	0.07
Male	112	65.9	14	56	107	75.4	124	63.3			
Female	58	34.1	11	44	35	24.6	72	36.7			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	F	df	p
Age (years)	18.45	5.6	17.80	4.9	16.38	5.30	17.19	5.9	3.812	3	0.01**
FSIQ	101.98	18.8	79.8	21.1	94.93	20.8	108.44	14.1	28.29	3	<2e-16***
Mean CT (mm)	2.67	0.12	2.67	0.13	2.69	0.14	2.68	0.11	1.07	3	0.36
Total SA (m²)	0.21	0.26	0.21	0.29	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	5.734	3	<0.001***

305 ^a ages range from 7-30 years in the ASD only group, from 10 to 30 years in the ADHD only
 306 group, from 7 to 29 years in the ASD+ADHD group and from 6 to 30 years in the typical
 307 developing group. Full-scale IQ ranged from 58 to 148 in the ASD only group, from 50 to 119
 308 in the ADHD only group, from 40 to 142 in the ASD x ADHD group and from 69 to 142 in the
 309 typical developing group.

310

311 **Main effect of ASD and ADHD on CT and SA**

312 Following RFT-based cluster-correction ($p < 0.05$, two-tailed), the main effect of autism was
313 associated with increased CT in the anterior-cingulate cortex (ACC; approximate Brodmann
314 areas (BA) 24/33), in the left superior and middle temporal gyrus (BA 21/22), and the right
315 precuneus cortex (BA 31). By contrast, autism was associated with decreased CT in the parietal
316 cortex (BA 7) and the middle frontal gyrus (BA 6/8/9) (Figure 1A). We also found that the
317 main effect of autism was associated with decreased SA in the right anterior-cingulate cortex
318 (BA 24/33) relative to non-autistic individuals (Figure 2A; Additional file: Table S2). For the
319 main effect of ADHD, we observed decreases in CT in right superior frontal gyrus (BA 6/8/9),
320 right cingulate cortex (BA 23/24/33), and the right precuneus cortex (BA 31) (Figure 1B).
321 ADHD was also associated with increased SA in left parahippocampal gyrus (BA 27/28) only
322 (Figure 2B; Additional file: Table S3; see Additional file: Figure S3 for unthresholded t-maps).
323 Vertex-level effect sizes (*Cohen's f*) for the main effects of autism and ADHD, and all other
324 model terms are displayed in the Additional file: Figure S4.

325

326 **Figure 1: Differences of cortical thickness for main effects of ASD, ADHD, and ASD-by-**
327 **ADHD interaction.** (A-C) Random field theory (RFT)-based cluster corrected t-maps ($p <$
328 0.05 , 2-tailed) for CT. (A) Significant decreases in CT in ASD compared to non-ASD are
329 displayed in blue and significant increases are displayed in orange (B) Significant decrease in

330 CT in ADHD compared to non-ADHD is displayed in blue and significant increase is displayed
 331 in orange (C) the ASD×ADHD interaction effect for CT (D) mean CT at right cingulate cortex
 332 for the interaction effect (E) mean CT at right temporal lobe for the interaction effect (F) mean
 333 CT at left parietal cortex for the interaction effect. Note: ASD: autism spectrum disorder;
 334 ADHD: attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder; TD: typically developing; t: t-statistic; CT:
 335 cortical thickness; L: left; R: right.

336

337

338 **Figure 2: Differences of surface area for main effects of ASD, ADHD, and ASD-by-ADHD**
 339 **interaction.** (A-C) Random field theory (RFT)-based cluster corrected t-maps ($p < 0.05$, 2-
 340 tailed) for SA. (A) Significant decrease in SA in ASD compared to non-ASD is displayed in
 341 blue and significant increase is displayed in orange (B) Significant decrease in SA in ADHD
 342 compared to non-ADHD is displayed in blue and significant increase is displayed in orange
 343 (C) the ASD×ADHD interaction effect for SA. (D) mean SA at right frontal gyrus for the
 344 interaction effect. Note: ASD: autism spectrum disorder; ADHD: attention-
 345 deficit/hyperactivity disorder; TD: typically developing; t: t-statistic; SA: surface area; L: left;
 346 R: right.

347

348 **Significant interactions between ASD and ADHD**

349 In addition to the main effects of group, we examined an ASD-by-ADHD interaction term. We
350 identified several cortical regions, where the neuroanatomy of autism (or ADHD) was
351 significantly modulated by co-occurring ADHD (or ASD) including the left parietal cortex (BA
352 7), precentral and superior frontal gyrus (BA 6/8), the right temporal gyrus (BA 20/21/22),
353 cingulate cortex (BA 23/24/33), and precuneus cortex (BA 31) for measures of CT (Figure 1C).
354 In these regions, we observed different types of interactions. For example, in the cingulate
355 cortex CT in the ASD+ADHD group was significantly increased compared to the other groups
356 (Figure 1D), whereas in the precentral gyrus CT in the ASD+ADHD group was significantly
357 decreased compared to all other groups (Figure 1F). We also found a significant cluster in the
358 right temporal gyrus with no significant difference between both ASD groups. Here, the
359 interaction was mainly driven by the difference between individuals with ADHD and TD
360 controls, which was significantly increased for measures of CT (Figure 1E; see Additional file:
361 Figure S5A for interaction plots of all significant clusters). For measures of SA, significant
362 differences in the right dorsolateral prefrontal gyrus (BA 46) (Figure 2C) were found. Here,
363 the interaction was mainly driven by the difference between individuals with ADHD and TD
364 controls, which was significantly decreased, while small or no differences were observed
365 between controls and both autism subgroups (Figure 2D; see Additional file: Figure S5B for
366 interaction plots of all significant clusters; Additional file: Table S4).

367

368 **Significant differences between ASD+ADHD and ASD only**

369 To specifically identify differences between the ASD+ADHD and the ASD only group, we
370 examined a subsample of individuals with ASD. We observed that individuals with
371 ASD+ADHD had significantly decreased CT relative to individuals with ASD only in the left

372 precentral, caudal middle frontal, and postcentral gyrus (BA 6/8/9) (Figure 3; Additional file:
373 Table S4). There were no significant differences for measures of SA.

374
375 **Figure 3: Differences of cortical thickness for ASD+ADHD vs. ASD-only. Random-field-**
376 **theory-based cluster-corrected t-maps ($p < 0.05$, 2-tailed).** (A) Significant decrease in CT
377 in ASD+ADHD compared to ASD-only is displayed in blue and significant increase is
378 displayed in orange (B) mean CT at left parietal cortex for the ASD+ADHD subgroup (blue)
379 and the ASD-only subgroup (yellow). Note: ASD: autism spectrum disorder; ADHD: attention-
380 deficit/hyperactivity disorder; t: t-statistic; CT: cortical thickness; L: left; R: right. ** $p < 0.01$.

381 382 Gene Set Enrichment Analyses

383 Here, we decoded the t-maps for the main effects of autism and ADHD, as well as the CT and
384 SA maps for the ASD-by-ADHD interaction terms (i.e. six maps in total). This resulted in sets
385 of (i) $N_{CT} = 598$ and $N_{SA} = 259$ significant genes associated with the main effect of autism for
386 CT and SA respectively, (ii) $N_{CT} = 272$ and $N_{SA} = 1005$ significant genes associated with the
387 main effect of ADHD, and (iii) $N_{CT} = 1258$ and $N_{SA} = 233$ significant genes associated with the
388 ASD-by-ADHD interaction term. Within these gene sets, we observed a significant enrichment
389 of genes known to be associated with autism, and particularly for genes that are known to be
390 differentially expressed in autism during childhood and adolescence (see Figure 4 for details).

391 More specifically, in all decoded CT maps (i.e., for main effect of autism, ADHD, and the
392 interaction term), we observed a significant enrichment of gene co-expression module
393 CTX.M20, which is known to be upregulated in the autism cortex and has been linked to Gene
394 Ontology terms representing developmental processes and the regulation of cell differentiation
395 (50). Moreover, we observed a significant enrichment of autism genes listed in the SFARI
396 database. Notably, there was no significant enrichment of autism- or ADHD-related risk genes
397 resulting from GWAS studies. However, these were also amongst the smallest gene sets tested
398 with only $N = 22$ genes for ADHD (Figure 4A & B).

399 Different gene sets were found to be enriched in the SA maps (Figure 4C & D). Here, in all
400 decoded maps, we observed an enrichment of gene co-expression module CTX.M16, which is
401 associated with neuronal markers and synaptic genes (53), and is known to be downregulated
402 in the autism cortex. In contrast to measures of CT, however, where most gene sets were
403 enriched in both main effects for autism and ADHD, gene set enrichments were more
404 prominent in the main effect of ADHD for measures of SA. Autism-related genes hence seem
405 to have a pattern of expression that more closely resembles the differences in CT in autism
406 rather than differences in SA. Moreover, autism-related genes are equally important to the
407 neuroanatomy underpinning ADHD symptomatology, particularly when examining measures
408 of SA. Gene sets resulting from the GLS decoding approach are shown in the Additional file:
409 Figure S6.

410 Overall (i.e., across gene sets), there was little overlap between genes significantly associated
411 with the main effect of ASD, ADHD, and/or the ASD-by-ADHD interaction terms on the
412 transcriptomic level (see Additional file: Figure S7). More specifically, a total of 1,3% of all
413 genes identified as being significantly enriched in any of the imaging phenotypes was shared
414 between the main effect of ASD and ADHD for measures of CT, and a total of 8.1% of genes
415 associated with these main effects for measures of SA.

Cortical Thickness

Surface Area

416

417 **Figure 4: Genomic underpinnings of neurodevelopmental deviations in cortical thickness**

418 **and surface area in ASD, ADHD, and ASD+ADHD.** Panel A and C show the t-maps of the

419 main effect of ASD, the main effect of ADHD and the ASD-by-ADHD interaction term for

420 measures of CT (A) and SA (C). Panel B (CT) and D (SA) show significant odds ratios at a

421 false discovery rate (FDR) corrected p threshold of 0.05 resulting from the gene set enrichment

422 analyses for genes expressed in the different output maps. Gene sets were subdivided into sets

423 with differential gene expression in ASD, sets representing ASD risk genes, and a set

424 representing ADHD risk genes. Gene sets are annotated and labeled based on their original

425 publication. ASD: autism spectrum disorder; ADHD: attention-deficit/hyperactivity-disorder;

426 CTX: cortex; DEG: differentially expressed gene; down: down-regulated expression in ASD;

427 up: upregulated expression in ASD; NGenes: number of genes in each gene set; CT: cortical

428 thickness; SA: surface area; *: $p < 0.05$ (FDR-corrected), **: $p < 0.01$ (FDR-corrected); red

429 squares indicate consistently significant enrichments across both approaches (see Additional

430 file: Figure S6).

431

432 **Discussion**

433 This study examined neuroanatomical differences between autistic individuals with and
434 without co-occurring ADHD relative to individuals with ADHD only and non-autistic controls.
435 Moreover, to bridge the gap between macroscopic and microscopic differences, we examined
436 whether the spatial patterns of neuroanatomical differences in CT and SA are enriched for
437 genes implemented in the etiology of autism and ADHD, and genes known to be differentially
438 expressed in autism. We established that it is possible to separate the effect of autism from the
439 effect of ADHD on the level of neuroanatomy based on measures of CT and SA. Notably, we
440 also observed significant ASD-by-ADHD interactions, and significant differences in CT
441 between ASD individuals with ADHD and those without. This suggests that the neuroanatomy
442 of ASD is significantly modulated by co-occurring ADHD. Further we showed a significant
443 association of autism and ADHD related patterns of neuroanatomical variability with autism-
444 but not ADHD-related genes. Our study thus provides important novel insights into the
445 neurobiological and putative genomics underpinning the complex clinical phenotype of autism.

446

447 **Main effect of ASD and ADHD on CT and SA**

448 Neuroanatomical differences in autism and ADHD are well documented and primarily affect
449 fronto-temporal and fronto-parietal regions for autism (2), as well as cingulate cortices for
450 ADHD (11). In the present study, we examined the neuroanatomical underpinnings of autism
451 and ADHD within a 2 x 2 factorial design that included (i) ASD individuals with co-occurring
452 ADHD, (ii) ASD only individuals, (iii) ADHD only individuals, and (iv) non-autistic controls.
453 While it remains a topic of debate whether autism should be encoded as a categorical variable
454 (54), this design allowed us to identify a set of brain regions where neuroanatomical variability
455 in CT and SA are uniquely attributable to either autism or ADHD. By examining both main

456 effects, we were able to separate autism from ADHD based on patterns of neuroanatomical
457 variability in fronto-temporal regions (e.g. left superior and middle temporal gyrus), and in
458 limbic and prefrontal regions (i.e. cingulate cortex, parahippocampal gyrus, and the superior
459 frontal gyrus). Many of the brain regions associated with the main effect of ASD have
460 previously been linked to the wider neural systems that mediate functions related to social
461 cognition and/or emotional processing, i.e. core autism traits (9). Prefrontal areas such as the
462 superior frontal gyrus, which showed significant differences in CT for the main effect of
463 ADHD, are important for executive functioning, attention and motor planning, which are all
464 functions known to be impaired in ADHD (55,56). Our findings of significant neuroanatomical
465 differences associated with ASD and ADHD are thus in line with previous reports using a
466 categorical approach, however, it does not rule out the necessity of future studies using
467 dimensional approaches. While a categorical approach is particularly well suited to examine
468 neuroanatomical differences associated with both ASD and ADHD (as well as their
469 interaction), future dimensional research would complement our study by accounting for the
470 inter-individual differences in the broader phenotypes of ASD and ADHD. To date, autism
471 diagnostic is still based on a categorical cut-off that remains largely unchanged across the
472 human life-span.

473 In addition, as studies examining the neuroanatomical underpinnings of autism and co-morbid
474 ADHD are still rare, and there is currently little knowledge on basic case-control differences,
475 elicited in adequately powered samples. In terms of ASD, several lines of ASD research also
476 converge in suggesting that the condition might be most effectively understood as a categorical
477 fixed effect rather than a dimensional construct (for review see (57)). For example, Frazier et
478 al. (58) examined several indicators of ASD (e.g., eye gaze metrics from social stimulus
479 paradigms), establishing a categorical data structure that closely corresponded to a diagnosis
480 of ASD across measures (58). ADHD, on the other hand, is widely considered a dimensional

481 construct with fluctuations in symptom severity and profiles across the human lifespan
482 (11,59,60). For example, only 15% of children with ADHD still show criteria for a diagnosis
483 during adulthood (60), and symptoms often also change from a more externalizing nature
484 during childhood to a more internalizing nature during adulthood (11,59). Future studies might
485 therefore benefit from employing both a categorical and a dimensional approach to examine
486 the neuroanatomy associated with ASD and ADHD.

487 The effect sizes associated with the main effect of ASD and ADHD were relatively small,
488 overall, and did not exceed a value of 0.2 on the vertex level. Small to medium effects
489 associated with between-group differences in neuroanatomy have previously been observed
490 even in large-scale neuroimaging studies with $N > 500$ that compare ASD or ADHD individuals
491 with neurotypical controls (12,14). The low effects reported by neuroimaging studies seem to
492 be driven by small differences in mean, and larger phenotypic variability in neurodiverse study
493 population (44), thus highlighting the significant inter-individual heterogeneity that is
494 characteristic for neurodevelopmental conditions on the level of etiology, neurobiology, and
495 symptomatology. Taken together, our findings indicate that autism and ADHD may have
496 separable neuroanatomical underpinnings that may mediate differences in clinical phenotypes.
497 The main effects of autism and ADHD are, however, only interpretable in the absence of a
498 significant ASD-by-ADHD interaction.

499

500 **Significant interactions between ASD and ADHD**

501 While previous studies have focused on the effects of ASD and ADHD in separate case-control
502 designs (14,61), we examined to what extent, and where in the brain, the neuroanatomy of ASD
503 is modulated by ADHD symptomatology (i.e. the ASD-by-ADHD interaction). We observed
504 a significant ASD-by-ADHD interaction term in the right temporal gyrus, the right cingulate
505 gyrus and the left precentral gyrus for measures of CT, and in the right dorsolateral prefrontal

506 gyrus for measures of SA. Some of these clusters (right temporal gyrus and right dorsolateral
507 prefrontal gyrus) were mainly driven by neuroanatomical differences between individuals with
508 ADHD only relative to controls, while small or no differences were observed between non-
509 autistic controls and autistic individuals (including those with co-occurring ADHD). ADHD-
510 related neuroanatomical variability in these brain regions thus seems to be modulated, or even
511 masked, by also having a diagnosis of autism. However, other clusters associated with the
512 ASD-by-ADHD interaction term, e.g., in the right cingulate gyrus and left precentral gyrus,
513 also showed significant differences between the ASD participants with co-occurring ADHD
514 and those with ASD only. A significant interaction between autism and ADHD indicates that
515 the neuroanatomical underpinnings of ADHD in autistic individuals cannot be explained by
516 either a diagnosis of autism or a diagnosis of ADHD alone.

517

518 **Significant differences between ASD+ADHD and ASD only**

519 Our additional analysis within the ASD±ADHD subsample showed significant differences
520 between both groups in the left precentral gyrus for measures of CT. Here, individuals with co-
521 occurring autism and ADHD had a significantly thinner cortex compared to those individuals
522 with autism alone. For measures of SA, no significant clusters for this contrast were observed.
523 Taken together, our findings suggest that (i) the neuroanatomy of autism is significantly
524 modulated by co-occurring ADHD symptomatology, and (ii) although ADHD is highly co-
525 occurring in autism, both conditions seem to have separable neuroanatomical underpinnings.

526

527 **Gene Set Enrichment Analyses**

528 In a next analysis step, we examined whether the patterns of CT and SA attributed to the main
529 effects and the interaction term are linked to the genetic etiology of autism or ADHD. Similar
530 to Romero-Garcia et al. (62), we found that all decoded CT maps were enriched for genes and

531 co-expression modules that have previously been implicated in the etiology of autism, and
532 particularly for genes associated with brain development and the regulation of cell
533 differentiation (50). For measures of SA, an enrichment of genes and co-expression modules
534 that are associated with neuronal markers and synaptic genes was found (53). Notably, the
535 pattern of neuroanatomical differences in SA associated with the main effect of ADHD also
536 showed a robust enrichment of autism-related genes, implying that these genes may not be
537 specific to autism, but may also affect the neuroanatomy of other neurodevelopmental
538 conditions such as ADHD.

539 This finding agrees with previous genetic studies demonstrating that ASD and ADHD are
540 genetically correlated, with a SNP-based genetic correlation of 0.37 (34). Many of the genetic
541 loci implicated in ASD and ADHD are therefore ‘pleiotropic’, i.e., can influence two or more
542 clinical phenotypes. Moreover, the effects of ASD susceptibility genes on the brain are known
543 to be pleiotropic, and may exert their influence via gene regulatory mechanisms during
544 childhood and adolescence (30,63,64). This could also account for highly individualized
545 patterns of neuroanatomical variations or ‘fingerprints’ that are commonly observed in ASD
546 (44). It is therefore possible that similar genotypes underpin distinct phenotypes, which could
547 explain why we observed an enrichment of ASD-related genes both in the ASD and ADHD
548 imaging phenotype, even though the neuroanatomical patterns characteristic for each
549 phenotype were different.

550 Moreover, while ASD and ADHD are known to be genetically related, little is currently known
551 about the functional involvement of genes that are specific to ASD and/or ADHD. Moreover,
552 distinct imaging phenotypes could be caused by more complex genetic interactions between
553 ASD- and ADHD-related genes, which cannot be identified based on the gene-set enrichment
554 analyses performed in the present study. This highlights the need for conducting future large-

555 scale genome wide association studies (GWAS) to link genetic variation associated with
556 neurodevelopmental conditions to differences in neuroanatomical phenotypes.

557 Also, while we observed a significant enrichment of autism-related genes, there was no
558 significant enrichment of ADHD risk genes in the main effect of ASD or ADHD. However,
559 the number of recognized ADHD-susceptibility genes remains as yet small, which limits the
560 statistical power of enrichment tests. Moreover, little is currently known about the functional
561 role of ADHD genes and their impact on cortical gene expression. Future genetic and/or
562 transcriptomic studies are therefore needed to provide further insights into the genomic
563 underpinnings of ADHD, and to expand the set of genes that might be utilized to link ADHD-
564 related differences in brain anatomy to putative underlying mechanisms.

565

566 **Limitations**

567 The present study needs to be interpreted in the light of several limitations. Although we
568 employed a multicenter design to overcome single-site recruitment limitations, our sample size
569 of $N = 25$ individuals in the ADHD only group is relatively small compared to the other
570 subgroups, which limits the generalizability of the results. Also, we assigned subjects into
571 ADHD positive groupings according to the DSM-5 rating scale. While this is sufficient for
572 obtaining a research diagnosis of ADHD, our approach did not take into account for how long
573 the symptoms have been present, which is typically considered when assessing ADHD in the
574 clinical setting. It will therefore be important to repeat our analyses in a bigger sample of pure
575 ADHD cohorts that were diagnosed according to clinical gold standards to make our study
576 comparable to previous findings in these cohorts. Furthermore, future studies employing a
577 dimensional approach are also required to provide a more nuanced picture of the heterogeneity
578 associated with autism. Last, our gene expression decoding analysis was based on the Allen
579 Human Brain Atlas (27), which is the most comprehensive gene expression atlas to date.

580 However, the Allen atlas is based on adult donors exclusively, and provides a coverage that is
581 significantly lower than the spatial resolution of our neuroimaging data. We therefore
582 acknowledge the importance of repeating the analyses in high-resolution age-specific gene-
583 expression data sets once these become available, to corroborate the important link between
584 molecular and macroscopic pathology in autism.

585 **Conclusion**

586 Our findings indicate that the neuroanatomy of ASD is significantly modulated by ADHD, and
587 that autistic individuals with co-occurring ADHD may have specific neuroanatomical
588 underpinnings potentially mediated by atypical gene expression.

589

590 **List of abbreviations**

591 ASD: Autism spectrum disorders; ADHD: attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder; GM: grey
592 matter; CT: cortical thickness; LEAP: Longitudinal European Project; SA : surface area;
593 AHBA: Allen Human Brain Atlas; SCZ: schizophrenia; GWAS: Genome-wide association
594 studies; SNP: single nucleotide polymorphisms; TD: typically developing; GLM: general
595 linear model; FSIQ: full scale IQ; ID: intellectual disability; RFT: random field theory; BA:
596 Brodmann areas

597

598 **Declarations**

599 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

600 An independent ethics committee at each site approved the study, and written informed consent
601 was obtained for all participants.

Site

Ethics committee

ID/

reference no.

KCL	London-Central and Queen Square Health Research Authority Research	13/LO/ 1156
UCAM	Ethics Committee	
RUNMC	Radboud universitair medisch centrum Instituut Waarborging Kwaliteit en Veiligheid Commissie Mensgebonden Onderzoek Regio Arnhem-Nijmegen	2013/455
UMCU	(Radboud University Medical Centre Institute Ensuring Quality and Safety Committee on Research Involving Human Subjects Arnhem-Nijmegen)	
CIMH	UMM Universitätsmedizin Mannheim, Medizinische Ethik Kommission II (UMM University Medical Mannheim, Medical Ethics Commission II)	2014- 540N- MA
UCBM	Universita Campus Bio-Medica De Roma Comitato Etico (University Campus Bio-Medical Ethics Committee De Roma)	18/14 PAR ComET CBM
KI	Centrala Etikprovningssamnden (Central Ethical Review Board)	32-2010

602

603 **Availability of data and materials**

604 Due to ethical restrictions, we are currently not able to make the data publicly available.

605 However, it is planned to release the data for perusal of the wider scientific community within

606 the next couple of years once legal requirements are in place.

607 **Competing interests**

608 The IMI-JU2 had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation

609 of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results. Any views

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611 has been in the past 3 years a consultant to/member of advisory board of/and/or speaker for

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648 **Authors' contributions**

649 The “European Autism Interventions - A Multicenter Study for Developing New Medications
650 (EU-AIMS) Longitudinal European Autism Project (LEAP)” group collaboratively collected
651 the data. LMB conceptualized the study and conceived the analysis plan with support from TS,
652 CG, and CE. LMB conducted the data analysis and wrote the first draft of manuscript. TS and
653 CE provided the software used for the analyses. JL, HS, AB, CMP, BO, EL, DLF, JKB, CFB,
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655 manuscript versions and agreed to the final draft. All authors read and approved the final
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673

674 **References**

- 675 1. American Psychiatric Association (APA). Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of
676 Mental Disorders (DSM-5®). 2013;
- 677 2. Ecker C, Bookheimer SY, Murphy DGM. Neuroimaging in autism spectrum
678 disorder: Brain structure and function across the lifespan. *Lancet Neurol.*
679 2015;14(11):1121–34.
- 680 3. van Rooij D, Anagnostou E, Arango C, Auzias G, Behrmann M, Busatto GF, et al.
681 Cortical and subcortical brain morphometry differences between patients with
682 autism spectrum disorder and healthy individuals across the lifespan: Results from
683 the ENIGMA ASD working group. *American Journal of Psychiatry.*
684 2018;175(4):359–69.
- 685 4. Ecker C. The neuroanatomy of autism spectrum disorder: An overview of structural
686 neuroimaging findings and their translatability to the clinical setting. In: *Autism.*
687 2017. p. 18–28.
- 688 5. Leyfer OT, Folstein SE, Bacalman S, Davis NO, Dinh E, Morgan J, et al. Comorbid
689 Psychiatric Disorders in Children with Autism: Interview Development and Rates
690 of Disorders. *J Autism Dev Disord.* 2006 Oct 15;36(7).

- 691 6. Hanson E, Cerban BM, Slater CM, Caccamo LM, Bacic J, Chan E. Brief Report:
692 Prevalence of Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder Among Individuals with an
693 Autism Spectrum Disorder. *J Autism Dev Disord*. 2013 Jun 13;43(6).
- 694 7. Baker BL, Blacher J. Disruptive Behavior Disorders in Adolescents With ASD:
695 Comparisons to Youth With Intellectual Disability or Typical Cognitive
696 Development. *J Ment Health Res Intellect Disabil*. 2015 Apr 3;8(2).
- 697 8. de Bruin EI, Ferdinand RF, Meester S, de Nijs PFA, Verheij F. High Rates of
698 Psychiatric Co-Morbidity in PDD-NOS. *J Autism Dev Disord*. 2007 May
699 20;37(5):877–86.
- 700 9. Blakemore SJ. The social brain in adolescence. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2008
701 Apr;9(4):267–77.
- 702 10. Hoogman M, Bralten J, Hibar DP, Mennes M, Zwiers MP, Schweren LSJ, et al.
703 Subcortical brain volume differences in participants with attention deficit
704 hyperactivity disorder in children and adults: a cross-sectional mega-analysis.
705 *Lancet Psychiatry*. 2017 Apr;4(4):310–9.
- 706 11. Faraone S V., Asherson P, Banaschewski T, Biederman J, Buitelaar JK, Ramos-
707 Quiroga JA, et al. Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*.
708 2015;1.
- 709 12. Hoogman M, Muetzel R, Guimaraes JP, Shumskaya E, Mennes M, Zwiers MP, et
710 al. Brain imaging of the cortex in ADHD: A coordinated analysis of large-scale
711 clinical and population-based samples. *American Journal of Psychiatry*.
712 2019;176(7):531–42.
- 713 13. Brieber S, Neufang S, Bruning N, Kamp-Becker I, Remschmidt H, Herpertz-
714 Dahlmann B, et al. Structural brain abnormalities in adolescents with autism

- 715 spectrum disorder and patients with attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Journal*
716 *of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*. 2007 Dec;48(12).
- 717 14. Park MTM, Raznahan A, Shaw P, Gogtay N, Lerch JP, Chakravarty MM.
718 Neuroanatomical phenotypes in mental illness: identifying convergent and
719 divergent cortical phenotypes across autism, ADHD and schizophrenia. *Journal of*
720 *Psychiatry and Neuroscience*. 2018 May 1;43(3):201–12.
- 721 15. Mizuno Y, Kagitani-Shimono K, Jung M, Makita K, Takiguchi S, Fujisawa TX, et
722 al. Structural brain abnormalities in children and adolescents with comorbid autism
723 spectrum disorder and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Transl Psychiatry*.
724 2019 Dec 9;9(1):332.
- 725 16. Mahajan R, Dirlikov B, Crocetti D, Mostofsky SH. Motor Circuit Anatomy in
726 Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder With or Without Attention Deficit
727 Hyperactivity Disorder. *Autism Research*. 2016;9(1):67–81.
- 728 17. Nickel K, Tebartz van Elst L, Manko J, Unterrainer J, Rauh R, Klein C, et al.
729 Inferior Frontal Gyrus Volume Loss Distinguishes Between Autism and
730 (Comorbid) Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder—A FreeSurfer Analysis in
731 Children. *Front Psychiatry*. 2018;9(October):1–11.
- 732 18. Ecker C, Murphy DGM. Neuroimaging in autism—from basic science to
733 translational research. *Nat Rev Neurol* [Internet]. 2014 Feb 14;10(2):82–91.
734 Available from: <http://www.nature.com/articles/nrneuro.2013.276>
- 735 19. Huttenlocher; Peter. Synaptic density in human frontal cortex — Developmental
736 changes and effects of aging. *Brain Res* [Internet]. 1979 Mar;163(2):195–205.
737 Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/0006899379903494>
- 738 20. Nemani JK, Kostovi I, Nemani O. Prenatal and Perinatal Development of Radial
739 Cell Columns in the Human Auditory Cortex. *Acta Otolaryngol* [Internet]. 1984

- 740 Jan 8;97(5–6):489–95. Available from:
741 <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.3109/00016488409132926>
- 742 21. Rakic P. Neuronal migration and contact guidance in the primate telencephalon.
743 *Postgrad Med J* [Internet]. 1978;54 Suppl 1:25–40. Available from:
744 <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/364453>
- 745 22. Pretzsch CM, Floris DL, Schäfer T, Bletsch A, Gurr C, Lombardo M V., et al.
746 Cross-sectional and longitudinal neuroanatomical profiles of distinct clinical
747 (adaptive) outcomes in autism. *Mol Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2023 Mar 29; Available
748 from: <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41380-023-02016-z>
- 749 23. Charman T, Loth E, Tillmann J, Crawley D, Wooldridge C, Goyard D, et al. The
750 EU-AIMS Longitudinal European Autism Project (LEAP): Clinical
751 characterisation. *Mol Autism*. 2017;8(1):1–21.
- 752 24. Wozniak RH, Leezenbaum NB, Northrup JB, West KL, Iverson JM. The
753 development of autism spectrum disorders: variability and causal complexity.
754 *Wiley Interdiscip Rev Cogn Sci*. 2017 Jan;8(1–2):e1426.
- 755 25. Joon P, Kumar A, Parle M. What is autism? *Pharmacological Reports*. 2021 Oct
756 10;73(5):1255–64.
- 757 26. Luo Y, Weibman D, Halperin JM, Li X. A Review of Heterogeneity in Attention
758 Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). *Front Hum Neurosci*. 2019 Feb 11;13.
- 759 27. Hawrylycz MJ, Lein ES, Guillozet-Bongaarts AL, Shen EH, Ng L, Miller JA, et al.
760 An anatomically comprehensive atlas of the adult human brain transcriptome.
761 *Nature*. 2012;489(7416):391–9.
- 762 28. Sandin S, Lichtenstein P, Kuja-Halkola R, Hultman CM, Larsson H, Reichenberg
763 A. The Heritability of Autism Spectrum Disorder. *JAMA*. 2017 Sep
764 26;318(12):1182.

- 765 29. Cross-Disorder Group of the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium. Genetic
766 relationship between five psychiatric disorders estimated from genome-wide SNPs.
767 Nat Genet. 2013 Sep 11;45(9):984–94.
- 768 30. Geschwind DH. Genetics of autism spectrum disorders. Trends Cogn Sci. 2011
769 Sep;15(9):409–16.
- 770 31. Gilman SR, Iossifov I, Levy D, Ronemus M, Wigler M, Vitkup D. Rare De Novo
771 Variants Associated with Autism Implicate a Large Functional Network of Genes
772 Involved in Formation and Function of Synapses. Neuron. 2011 Jun;70(5):898–
773 907.
- 774 32. Huguet G, Benabou M, Bourgeron T. The Genetics of Autism Spectrum Disorders.
775 In: Sassone-Corsi P, Christen Y, editors. A Time for Metabolism and Hormones.
776 Springer; 2016. p. 101–29.
- 777 33. Demontis D, Walters GB, Athanasiadis G, Walters R, Therrien K, Farajzadeh L, et
778 al. Genome-wide analyses of ADHD identify 27 risk loci, refine the genetic
779 architecture and implicate several cognitive domains. medRxiv.
780 2022;15:2022.02.14.22270780.
- 781 34. Cross-Disorder Group of the Psychiatric Genomics Consortium. Genomic
782 Relationships, Novel Loci, and Pleiotropic Mechanisms across Eight Psychiatric
783 Disorders. Cell. 2019 Dec;179(7):1469-1482.e11.
- 784 35. Rommelse NNJ, Franke B, Geurts HM, Hartman CA, Buitelaar JK. Shared
785 heritability of attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder and autism spectrum
786 disorder. Eur Child Adolesc Psychiatry. 2010 Mar 11;19(3):281–95.
- 787 36. American Psychiatric Association (APA). Diagnostic and statistical manual of
788 mental disorders. 1994;
- 789 37. Association AP. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders. 2000;

- 790 38. WH. O. The ICD-10 Classification of mental and behavioural disorders: diagnostic
791 criteria for research. 1993,2013.
- 792 39. Dale AM, Fischl B, Sereno MI. Cortical Surface-Based Analysis. *Neuroimage*.
793 1999 Feb;9(2):179–94.
- 794 40. Fischl B, Sereno MI, Dale AM. Cortical Surface-Based Analysis. *Neuroimage*.
795 1999 Feb;9(2):195–207.
- 796 41. Ségonne F, Dale AM, Busa E, Glessner M, Salat D, Hahn HK, et al. A hybrid
797 approach to the skull stripping problem in MRI. *Neuroimage*. 2004 Jul;22(3):1060–
798 75.
- 799 42. Jovicich J, Czanner S, Greve D, Haley E, van der Kouwe A, Gollub R, et al.
800 Reliability in multi-site structural MRI studies: Effects of gradient non-linearity
801 correction on phantom and human data. *Neuroimage*. 2006 Apr;30(2):436–43.
- 802 43. Fischl B, Dale AM. Measuring the thickness of the human cerebral cortex from
803 magnetic resonance images. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*.
804 2000 Sep 26;97(20):11050–5.
- 805 44. Ecker C, Pretzsch CM, Bletsch A, Mann C, Schaefer T, Ambrosino S, et al.
806 Interindividual Differences in Cortical Thickness and Their Genomic
807 Underpinnings in Autism Spectrum Disorder. *American Journal of Psychiatry*.
808 2021;(7):appi.ajp.2021.2.
- 809 45. Winkler AM, Sabuncu MR, Yeo BTT, Fischl B, Greve DN, Kochunov P, et al.
810 Measuring and comparing brain cortical surface area and other areal quantities.
811 *Neuroimage*. 2012 Jul;61(4):1428–43.
- 812 46. Gorgolewski KJ, Fox AS, Chang L et al. Tight fitting genes: finding relations
813 between statistical maps and gene expression patterns [Internet]Hamburg,. In 2014.
814 Available from: <https://f1000research.com/posters/1097120>

- 815 47. Satterstrom FK, Kosmicki JA, Wang J, Breen MS, De Rubeis S, An JY, et al.
816 Large-Scale Exome Sequencing Study Implicates Both Developmental and
817 Functional Changes in the Neurobiology of Autism. *Cell*. 2020 Feb;180(3):568-
818 584.e23.
- 819 48. Gandal MJ, Zhang P, Hadjimichael E, Walker RL, Chen C, Liu S, et al.
820 Transcriptome-wide isoform-level dysregulation in ASD, schizophrenia, and
821 bipolar disorder. *Science* (1979) [Internet]. 2018 Dec 14;362(6420). Available
822 from: <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.aat8127>
- 823 49. Velmeshev D, Schirmer L, Jung D, Haeussler M, Perez Y, Mayer S, et al. Single-
824 cell genomics identifies cell type-specific molecular changes in autism. *Science*
825 (1979) [Internet]. 2019 May 17;364(6441):685–9. Available from:
826 <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.aav8130>
- 827 50. Parikshak NN, Swarup V, Belgard TG, Irimia M, Ramaswami G, Gandal MJ, et al.
828 Genome-wide changes in lncRNA, splicing, and regional gene expression patterns
829 in autism. *Nature*. 2016;540(7633):423–7.
- 830 51. Watanabe K, Taskesen E, van Bochoven A, Posthuma D. Functional mapping and
831 annotation of genetic associations with FUMA. *Nat Commun*. 2017 Nov
832 28;8(1):1826.
- 833 52. Watanabe K. FUMA SNP2GENE Tutorial [Internet]. Available from:
834 <https://fuma.ctglab.nl/tutorial#magma>
- 835 53. Kissel LT, Werling DM. Neural Transcriptomic Analysis of Sex Differences in
836 Autism Spectrum Disorder: Current Insights and Future Directions. *Biol*
837 *Psychiatry*. 2022 Jan;91(1):53–60.

- 838 54. Gudbrandsen M, Bletsch A, Mann C, Daly E, Murphy CM, Stoencheva V, et al.
839 Neuroanatomical underpinnings of autism symptomatology in carriers and non-
840 carriers of the 22q11.2 microdeletion. *Mol Autism*. 2020;11(1):1–15.
- 841 55. Shaw P, Eckstrand K, Sharp W, Blumenthal J, Lerch JP, Greenstein D, et al.
842 Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder is characterized by a delay in cortical
843 maturation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 2007 Dec
844 4;104(49):19649–54.
- 845 56. Castellanos FX, Tannock R. Neuroscience of attention-deficit/hyperactivity
846 disorder: the search for endophenotypes. *Nat Rev Neurosci*. 2002 Aug;3(8):617–
847 28.
- 848 57. Coghill D, Sonuga-Barke EJS. Annual research review: Categories versus
849 dimensions in the classification and conceptualisation of child and adolescent
850 mental disorders - Implications of recent empirical study. *J Child Psychol*
851 *Psychiatry*. 2012;53(5):469–89.
- 852 58. Frazier TW, Chetcuti L, Al-Shaban FA, Haslam N, Ghazal I, Klingemier EW, et
853 al. Categorical versus dimensional structure of autism spectrum disorder: A multi-
854 method investigation. *JCPP Advances*. 2023 Feb 21;
- 855 59. Matte B, Rohde LA, Grevet EH. ADHD in adults: a concept in evolution. *ADHD*
856 *Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorders*. 2012 Jun 16;4(2):53–62.
- 857 60. Faraone S V., Biederman J, Mick E. The age-dependent decline of attention deficit
858 hyperactivity disorder: a meta-analysis of follow-up studies. *Psychol Med*. 2006
859 Feb 3;36(2):159–65.
- 860 61. Dougherty CC, Evans DW, Myers SM, Moore GJ, Michael AM. A Comparison of
861 Structural Brain Imaging Findings in Autism Spectrum Disorder and Attention-
862 Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder. *Neuropsychol Rev*. 2016 Mar 19;26(1):25–43.

- 863 62. Romero-Garcia R, Warrier V, Bullmore ET, Baron-Cohen S, Bethlehem RAI.
864 Synaptic and transcriptionally downregulated genes are associated with cortical
865 thickness differences in autism. *Mol Psychiatry*. 2019;24(7):1053–64.
- 866 63. Courchesne E, Pramparo T, Gazestani VH, Lombardo M V., Pierce K, Lewis NE.
867 The ASD Living Biology: from cell proliferation to clinical phenotype. *Mol*
868 *Psychiatry* [Internet]. 2019 Jan 22;24(1):88–107. Available from:
869 <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41380-018-0056-y>
- 870 64. Parikshak NN, Luo R, Zhang A, Won H, Lowe JK, Chandran V, et al. Integrative
871 Functional Genomic Analyses Implicate Specific Molecular Pathways and Circuits
872 in Autism. *Cell* [Internet]. 2013 Nov;155(5):1008–21. Available from:
873 <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0092867413013494>

874

875 **Figure legends**

876 **Figure 2: Differences of cortical thickness for main effects of ASD, ADHD, and ASD-by-**
877 **ADHD interaction.** (A-C) Random field theory (RFT)-based cluster corrected t -maps ($p <$
878 0.05 , 2-tailed) for CT. (A) Significant decreases in CT in ASD compared to non-ASD are
879 displayed in blue and significant increases are displayed in orange (B) Significant decrease in
880 CT in ADHD compared to non-ADHD is displayed in blue and significant increase is displayed
881 in orange (C) the ASD \times ADHD interaction effect for CT (D) mean CT at right cingulate cortex
882 for the interaction effect (E) mean CT at right temporal lobe for the interaction effect (F) mean
883 CT at left parietal cortex for the interaction effect. Note: ASD: autism spectrum disorder;
884 ADHD: attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder; TD: typically developing; t : t -statistic; CT:
885 cortical thickness; L: left; R: right.

886 **Figure 2: Differences of surface area for main effects of ASD, ADHD, and ASD-by-ADHD**
887 **interaction.** (A-C) Random field theory (RFT)-based cluster corrected t -maps ($p < 0.05$, 2-

888 tailed) for SA. (A) Significant decrease in SA in ASD compared to non-ASD is displayed in
889 blue and significant increase is displayed in orange (B) Significant decrease in SA in ADHD
890 compared to non-ADHD is displayed in blue and significant increase is displayed in orange
891 (C) the ASD×ADHD interaction effect for SA. (D) mean SA at right frontal gyrus for the
892 interaction effect. Note: ASD: autism spectrum disorder; ADHD: attention-
893 deficit/hyperactivity disorder; TD: typically developing; t: t-statistic; SA: surface area; L: left;
894 R: right.

895 **Figure 3: Differences of cortical thickness for ASD+ADHD vs. ASD-only. Random-field-**
896 **theory-based cluster-corrected t-maps ($p < 0.05$, 2-tailed).** (A) Significant decrease in CT
897 in ASD+ADHD compared to ASD-only is displayed in blue and significant increase is
898 displayed in orange (B) mean CT at left parietal cortex for the ASD+ADHD subgroup (blue)
899 and the ASD-only subgroup (yellow). Note: ASD: autism spectrum disorder; ADHD: attention-
900 deficit/hyperactivity disorder; t: t-statistic; CT: cortical thickness; L: left; R: right. ** $p < 0.01$.

901 **Figure 4: Genomic underpinnings of neurodevelopmental deviations in cortical thickness**
902 **and surface area in ASD, ADHD, and ASD+ADHD.** Panel A and C show the t-maps of the
903 main effect of ASD, the main effect of ADHD and the ASD-by-ADHD interaction term for
904 measures of CT (A) and SA (C). Panel B (CT) and D (SA) show significant odds ratios at a
905 false discovery rate (FDR) corrected p threshold of 0.05 resulting from the gene set enrichment
906 analyses for genes expressed in the different output maps. Gene sets were subdivided into sets
907 with differential gene expression in ASD, sets representing ASD risk genes, and a set
908 representing ADHD risk genes. Gene sets are annotated and labeled based on their original
909 publication. ASD: autism spectrum disorder; ADHD: attention-deficit/hyperactivity-disorder;
910 CTX: cortex; DEG: differentially expressed gene; down: down-regulated expression in ASD;
911 up: upregulated expression in ASD; NGenes: number of genes in each gene set; CT: cortical
912 thickness; SA: surface area; *: $p < 0.05$ (FDR-corrected), **: $p < 0.01$ (FDR-corrected); red

913 squares indicate consistently significant enrichments across both approaches (see Additional
914 file: Figure S6).

915 **Additional files**

916 **Additional file: Supplementary Methods. 1.** Sample Description. **2.** MRI Data Quality
917 Assessments. **3.** Effects of Intellectual Disability. **4.** Site effects. **5.** General Least Square
918 (GLS)-decoding accounting for autocorrelations in spatially embedded transcriptomic maps.
919 **Supplementary Figure S1A.** Effects of Intellectual Disability (ID) for measures of cortical
920 thickness (CT). **Supplementary Figure S1B.** Effects of Intellectual Disability (ID) for
921 measures of cortical thickness (CT). **Supplementary Figure S1C.** Effects of Intellectual
922 Disability (ID) for measures of surface area (SA). **Supplementary Figure S1D.** Effects of
923 Intellectual Disability (ID) for measures of surface area (SA). **Supplementary Figure S2A.**
924 Effects of acquisition sites for measures of cortical thickness (CT). **Supplementary Figure**
925 **S2B.** Effects of acquisition sites for measures of cortical thickness (CT). **Supplementary**
926 **Figure S2C.** Effects of acquisition sites for measures of surface area (SA). **Supplementary**
927 **Figure S2D.** Effects of acquisition sites for measures of surface area (SA). **Supplementary**
928 **Figure S3.** Significant differences of cortical thickness (CT) and surface area (SA) for the main
929 effects of ASD, ADHD and the ASD-by-ADHD interaction term. **Supplementary Figure S4.**
930 Effect size plots for individual model terms. **Supplementary Figure S5A.** Interaction plots for
931 all significant clusters for measures of cortical thickness (CT). **Supplementary Figure S5B.**
932 Interaction plots for all significant clusters for measures of surface area (SA). **Supplementary**
933 **Figure S6.** Gene enrichments as resulting from the GLS-decoding approach **Supplementary**
934 **Figure S7.** Overlap between significant decoded genes. **Supplementary Table S1.** MRI
935 Acquisition Parameters across sites. **Supplementary Table S2.** Vertex-wise differences in CT
936 and SA for the main effect of ASD. **Supplementary Table S3.** Vertex-wise differences in CT
937 and SA for the main effect of ADHD. **Supplementary Table S4.** Vertex-wise differences in

938 CT and SA for the ASD-by-ADHD interaction term. **Supplementary Table S5.** Vertex-wise
939 differences in CT for the main effect of ASD+ADHD.

940

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